

VALIDATION OF THE ORGANIC NATURE OF ORIENTAL LANGUAGES: ANALYSIS OF “TIME IS MONEY” METAPHOR IN ENGLISH AND KHOWAR

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines a general level of consensus of culture amongst the European and Khowar speaking communities. It aims to show the common psychological understanding of the world as well as the mutually shared characteristics in both English and Khowar languages. Hence, it offers a comparative analysis of the different metaphors of time used in English and Khowar, in order to shed light on similarities and differences in conceptualizing the time metaphorically. The conceptual metaphors used in this research include mostly taken from the every-day expressions. The qualitative content analysis was the method of the study by paying attention to unique themes that illustrate the range of the meanings of the phenomenon rather than the statistical significance of the occurrence of particular texts or concepts. Hence, it critically analysis the queries, such as: how the defined model of the concept of time in terms of the anther, i.e., ‘TIME IS MONEY’. Here the concept of ‘TIME’ is understood in terms of ‘MONEY’. By keeping in view, the theoretical framework “Metaphors we live By, based on the Lakoff and Johnson (1980). Thus, the finding showed that Khowar is organic, generative processing and living language like English in the expression TIME IS MOREY metaphor.

Keywords: Metaphor, Time, Money, Expression, Organic, Processing and Generative

INTRODUCTION

The study of metaphors, historically begins with the evolution of the interactive theory of metaphor; and culminates in modern conceptual metaphor, which reflects a marked change in people’s view about the link between language, mind, and society (Gibbs, 1994). Aristotle, the pioneer in metaphorical studies states that metaphors play a deviant and anomalous rhetorical role to serve as an ornament and emotive instrument (Aristotle, 1992). It shows that metaphors are nothing more than a tool of embellishment in language. Keeping in view of the above notion, some

studies in this regard were carried out focusing on language only without taking into consideration the socio-cultural and ideological dynamics. Subsequently, Lakoff and Jonson (1980) challenged this perspective of metaphors in their work titled “Metaphor We Live By”. In this systematic groundbreaking study, they draw close attention to the relationship between language and thought (Lakoff & Jonson, 1980). They persuasively argue that metaphors are not merely the tools of embellishment in language but a conceptual art and the way of

defining one thing in terms of another (Lakoff & Jonson, 1980). In this way, Conceptual metaphors are an essential and indispensable phenomenon in language as well as in thought (Gibbs, 1994). Hence, metaphors are the integral part of any human language as they help the language user to understand the world around them by shaping their perceptions and framing their thoughts in a concrete shape with the help of similarities and difference between different objects (Sharma, 2012). The metaphors have two elements, tenor and vehicle. The tenor is the underlying literal meaning, whereas the vehicle is the image conveyed by the word actually used (Shah, Samad & Wali 2021). It helps to articulate abstract thought processes in a simple manner for easy comprehension of difficult concepts (Sharma, 2012). The conceptual metaphor often appears, when an abstract concept is being conversed, because it might at times be difficult to describe as it is. Therefore, the conceptual metaphors help to convey the exact message precisely. A metaphor may conventionally be recognized as a linguistic trend and cognitive tool for colloquial usage by different speech communities for the conceptualizations of various domains of information. Similarly, the world around us shapes our emotions. It's therefore, assumed that the emotions of human beings are neither predetermined nor innate but rational (Györi, 1998). Emotions are structured by concepts and judgments that people learn in a specific culture through which they give their experiences particular shapes and meanings (Györi, 1998). Thus, cultural influences shape a language considerably and metaphors agree with the cultural-environment and historical-background (Lakoff, 1980). Consequently, cultural-models play important role in comprehending the world around us and induce us to use a metaphorical language (Yu, 1998). Indeed, Conceptual metaphor embodies the manner of thoughts and influences every individual in taking cognizance of the world around them. Though, the nature of some of the conceptual metaphors across the nations may be different and reflect opposite cultural meanings, connotations, and ways of thinking (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Besides, they emphasize that the conceptual metaphor involves both of the ways of telling and thinking about phenomena. On the other hand, Lee (2001: 7) describes those conceptual metaphors are in fact, a prime manifestation of

cognitive entitlement that both language and thought are indissolubly interconnected.

The paper examines a general level of consensus of culture amongst the European and Khowar speaking communities. It aims to show the common psychological understanding of the world as well as the mutually shared characteristics in both English and Khowar languages. Hence, it offers a comparative analysis of the different metaphors of time used in English and Khowar, in order to shed light on similarities and differences in conceptualizing the time metaphorically. The conceptual metaphors used in this research include mostly taken from the everyday expressions. Hence, it critically analysis the queries, such as: how the defined model of the concept of time in terms of the anther, i.e., 'TIME IS MONEY'. Here the concept of 'TIME' is understood in terms of 'MONEY'.

Subsequently, English is an international language spoken all over the world with millions of users, who have adopted it as a first or second language. The English language is rich in metaphors and a sizeable work has been done on conceptual metaphors by a number of writers, who have produced a literature of great merit (Shah, S. A. A., Shah, I. A., & Ahmad, G. 2021).

It is a living language used by the majority of the entire world for international means of communication, so there is hardly any comparison between English and other oriental languages (Said, 1971). On the other hand, Khowar is a language spoken by a small community confined to a mountainous region, which is hardly accessible to the outside world due to its harsh terrain (Decker, 1992; 28). Until recent times Khowar even did not exist in written form although it is a very rich language in terms of all the conventions that are attributed to any indigenous community. It has been a language of a tribal society, deprived of formal education since its inceptions; therefore, it did not grow much academically and mostly remained static due to scarcity of research on the various attributes and components of Khowar.

Though Khowar is one of the major languages of Northern Pakistan it is mainly spoken in Chitral, which is strategically located right in the center of different cultures with distinctive languages (Shah, S. A. A., Sharar, T. U., & us Samad, A. 2019). It has close cultural ties with Central Asian countries on the northern side and shares the same bond with Asian

countries in the south (Warburton, 2007) making it a repository of various cultures. Therefore, Khowar has a rich linguistic diversity encompassing all the cultures and languages that it has encountered. Although, majority of the population uses Khowar language as a vehicle of thought and they prefer to call themselves as Chitralis (Magnus, 2005). As compared to English, no linguistic study of Khowar has so far been made except that a few individuals initiated some sort of investigation into this language at a personal level for their own interest (Ali Shah, S. A., & Wali, M. I. (2021). The reason why no such task was undertaken seems to be the lack of easy access to Chitral; in the first place as high mountain ranges like the Hindu Kush, Karakorum and Himalayas broke communication links for a good part of the year (Curzon, 2012). Even those who worked on the Khowar language obtained information from outside resources instead of physically accessing the region (Curzon, 2012). Correspondingly, an effort has yet to be made in Khowar on the metaphorical aspect of the language and no study has ever been conducted in this regard leaving a big gap to be bridged if a comparison is to be made with the English language on the use of conceptual metaphors in expressing time is money (Shah, S. A. A., & Samad, A. U. 2018). Like all other communities living in cultural pocket holes, Chitralis have also developed distinctive physical experiences and cultivated peculiar metaphorical expressions, so the purpose of this paper is to identify any similarities and variations in the use of the conceptual Metaphor "TIME IS MONEY in English and Khowar in order to discover the universal or cultural-based values. Besides, the study aims to fill the gap yet unbridged. Moreover, it contributes to the existing literature on metaphors study. Moreover, it is important to show the organic, generative processing nature of all the oriental language, which was previously denied by the imperialists; keeping in view, the theoretical framework of the study, based on the Lakoff and Johnson (1980) branded of conceptual metaphor. Besides, this study contributes in understanding the economic terms metaphorically in the field of Economics.

Significance of the Study:

The significance of this research is that no such study based on conceptual metaphors of TIME IS MONEY in English and Khowar has yet been conducted. As metaphors have been considered 'a set of logical mapping structurally. However, the shared emotion metaphors in English and Khowar exhibit deviations as well similarities in the metaphorical expression. Besides, the study is significant in term to contribute the existing literature on the topic. Moreover, it provides a precocious measure of preventing the cultural traits of the regional language Khowar in the phase of global (English) before extinction by showing its organic nature.

Objectives of the study:

Objectively, this study explored cultural shades of meaning found in the emotion metaphors in English and Khowar languages as TIME IS MONE. Secondly, it compared and analogized the meaning of these conceptual metaphors in English and Khowar. Besides, to explore the organic entity of Khowar language.

Research Questions:

The study answered the following research question i.e., what cultural shades of meaning, and similarities as well as contrasts were found in the conceptual metaphors TIME IS MONEY in English and Khowar? Weather Khowar is a generative processing organic language like English or not?

Delimitation of the Study:

The study was delimited for the exploration of the conceptual metaphors TIME IS MONEY in English Khowar. Besides, the other related metaphors could not be covered under this study.

Methodology:

This study is qualitative, which is one of the types of scientific research. Creswell (1998) described that the qualitative research is an inquiry process to explore social or human problems. The researcher builds a complex, holistic picture, analyzes words, reports detailed views of informants, and conducts the study in a natural setting. The aforementioned literature provided the basic conceptual foundation of the qualitative study, which helped me in establishing the paradigm to this research article.

Qualitative Content Analysis: The qualitative content analysis is the method of the study. In this research article the interpretation of the text data was systematically classified through coding. Hsieh and Shannon (2005) defined qualitative content analysis as “a research method for the subjective interpretation of the content of text data through the systematic classification process of coding and identifying themes or patterns” (p.1278). Thus, the qualitative content analysis was the most suitable method for this study. As the qualitative content analysis pays attention to unique themes that illustrate the range of the meanings of the phenomenon rather than the statistical significance of the occurrence of particular texts or concepts. Data Collection Strategy Data collection is a key aspect of every research. Inaccurate data collection can impact the results of a study and ultimately lead to invalid results. In the proposed study I reviewed textual data for data collection. I selected text purposively. It means the text was selected on the bases of its relevance to the objectives and questions. Hence, the data was obtained from select books, Journal, indigenous texts of folklores, poetry and analytical works of both local and international scholars on the topic. Hence, the data was qualitatively analyzed through careful reading and rereading, the textual data coding and sorting the coded segments into broader categories as well as themes. Keeping in view, the theoretical framework of the study, based on the Lakoff and Johnson (1980) branded of conceptual metaphor.

Discussion:

The discussion examined universality and variation “TIME IS MONEY” metaphors in English and Khowar languages. As, language is one of the main components of culture, which lays an intellectual foundation of nationalism, perspective shaping and ways of thinking of a nation. As it is claimed by some of the western scholars that the oriental languages are inorganic, while English is an organic, generative processing living language. Hence, the discussion is a test case to insure the validity of the aforementioned claim. Henceforth, the following data in hand have been analyzed from both the languages.

TIME IS MONEY:

English: Don't waste your time.

Khowar: tan waqto zaya mo ko. (lit. Don't waste your time).

English: Please give me a little more time.

Khowar: mat pokro wa tam dat. (lit. give me a little more time).

English: How do you spend your time?

Khowar: ta waqt keycha shakhchoran. (lit. how do you spend your time).

English: I invested a lot of time in this project.

Khowar: awa haya korma tan ba waqto laga asum. (lit. I invested a lot of time).

English: The traffic this morning cost me two hours.

Khowar: traffic ma ju ganta zaya hoi. (lit. The traffic this morning cost me two hours).

English: You should budget your time.

Khowar: tan waqto bach kora, (lit. You should budget your time).

English: Time is gold.

Khowar: waqt surmosar de qemat. (lit. time is more precious than gold).

English: Thanks for your precious time.

Khowar: ta qimati waqto bach bo shokria. (lit. thanks for your precious time).

Specific conceptual metaphors TIME IS MONEY in Khowar:

The data showed that in Khowar language, there are specific conceptual metaphors to express time is money, as following:

Khowar: Saro molo uogh of shokchtiay. (lit. the water has flown under the Bridge).

Khowar: Daghio Chamout dona. (lit. to keep the figure of repentance on teeth).

Khowar: Hosh no koritm tan daqiyou hanisa pashman. (lit. I didn't know the time of youth that is why regret).

Khowar: shom xourota key zewar. (lit. it is the wastage of time to make jewelry for the irresponsible daughter).

Khowar: shom xawota key yaraq. (lit, it is a wastage of time to purchase weapon for the irresponsible son).

The aforementioned emotion metaphors of Love seemed to be common in colloquial usage and literature considerably, whereas in Khowar these seemed to be more elevated and mostly used in literature rather than colloquially. Thus, the chart exhibits the similarities in the major themes of metaphors time is money, but it also highlights the significant cultural as well as linguistic contrast. Hence, to understand these emotion metaphors might deepen cross cultural insight in to the concept of the perception and expression of TIME IS MONEY. According to the cultural influences the conceptual metaphors TIME IS MONEY in English may stem from individualistic views and media. On the other hand, Khowar speech community seemed to be influenced by Kalash tradition and therefore linking to the expressions with major visible entities like river, weapon, jewelry etc. Eventually, the metaphors seemed to be more expressive. On the other hand, these metaphoric expressions time is money in English seemed to be straightforward as compare to Khowar.

Conclusion:

This study is a step towards the process of successfully analyzing TIME IS MONEY metaphors in English and Khowar languages, which may help in the integration of the local (Khowar) and global (English) on a multifaceted level. Language takes root from the cognitive structure of the people, and according to their perception of the things they talk about and is the joining point of various experiences in diverse fields (Richards, 1936). The cognitive structure gained from daily experiences has constituted the psychological-basis performance of language. In this

study the metaphorical expressions TIME IS MONEY has been noticed that English and Khowar shared most of the Central-Metaphor with very slight variations in translation. Besides, the range of the metaphors in Khowar is as wider and richer as in English. Despite the fact that Khowar is a relatively young language as far as its codified written form is concerned. Some of the written documents of Khowar came into existence in the latter half of the 20th century, but the literary works of English date back to the 15th century. It can, therefore, be said that this study established the aforementioned claim on the basis that none of the Central-Metaphors is missing in Khowar. Though English and Khowar belong to two different language families and cultures, still both languages shared similarities in the Metaphor TIME IS MONEY. It seems that the similarity between English and Khowar is due to human-conceptualization that influence certain universal-properties of the human body. Here the properties refer to the embodiment of meanings: and the meanings reflect the human beings' collective biological capacities as well as physical and social experiences in their environments. Thus, these capabilities, as well as practices, are universal which help in articulation of human emotions throughout the world. It might be therefore the similarity in the expressions of emotion that conceptual metaphors in English and Khowar are quite natural. It might be because of the metaphorical concepts, which are embodied, either based on bodily experiences of the human being or physiological functioning of the human body's close relation. Hence, these similarities substantiate those metaphors aren't erratic but are embodied and motivated by the physiological truth,

Hence, in both case the findings reveal the organic nature of Khowar language like that of English. Contrary, variations also exist in the conceptualizations of these metaphors, which seem to be the influences of concrete-historical as well as conventional-culture reasons. It is obvious that culture shapes and influences in making the concepts and cognition of the world around the inhabitants. Thus, the finding showed that Khowar is organic, generative processing language like English in the expression TIME IS MOREY metaphor.

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